

MEANS OF VERBALIZING THE CONCEPT “FIRE” AND “WATER” IN ENGLISH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6579023>

Gavhar Bobomurodovna

Student of Uzswlu Izomova

Abstract: *The article deals with lexical means of representation of the English concepts “fire” and “water”. When analyzing English literary sources and dictionaries, it is found that the English concepts “fire” and “water” were verbalized using ten words of different roots. The article shows that each of them denoted a certain type of fire and water. Such diversity speaks of the special role of this concept in the culture of the people and in the minds of native speakers.*

Key words: *cognitive processes, fire, water, concept, models of the world, structural-semiotic approach, psychological state of a person,*

The study of the verbalization of concepts is one of the topical areas of modern linguistics. In linguistics, from the end of the 20th century to the present, there has been a general desire to study the language not on its own, by itself, but in connection with a person and his cognitive processes, since language is one of the ways of cognition and transmission of knowledge about reality. Considering English words derived from “fire”, we see that this concept had a negative value connotation. Words like torment, death by fire, fiery horror, killing fire, fiery disease, fever, martial fire verbalize people's fear of this phenomenon. Based on this, in the Christian period part of the concept of “fire” was not only “danger”, but also “punishment of sinners in hell.” In this regard, the former names of fire in the texts of the Christian period designate “fire of hell” already without distinction between themselves. However, the very image of “the fire that punishes sinners after death” is a continuation of the all-German mythological stories about the end of the world.

The symbolic-sign models of the world, embedded in the human mind and, accordingly, in the language, determine the rules of behavior for the individual and entire teams, and it is the team that exercises control over the preservation and the transmissibility of these models and over “the ways of introducing them into a person”, “taking care of uniformity and following these models”. The use of the structural-semiotic approach already

generally recognized in ethnolinguistic theory, following Vyach. Sun. Ivanov, V. M. Toporov, O. V. Tishchenko, T. V. Tsivyan and others, makes it possible highlight clear semantic oppositions in the reconstruction of content ancient Slavic and the sacred world of Christianity, trace the interaction and describe some systems through the prism of others. Since the main oppositions of the type as water-fire, life - death, happiness - misfortune, determine the program of behavior of each of the members of the society, they are reflected to a greater or lesser extent in the semantics of different levels of the language system, as well as in other semiotic systems.

The core of the image of water includes the following range of meanings: an all-consuming chthonic element, a symbol of fertility, reproduction, a symbol of cleansing and regenerating power, a symbol of the beginning and end of all things, a mediator between life and death, symbol of love, health, keeper of sacred information, spatial niche of mythological worlds. Water was represented as living element, ambivalent in relation to people, which could act as a saving, sacred principle and at the same time be a source evil, doom, death. This is the important role of the water element as an attribute of the psychological state of a person.

Parallels of two waters in English culture is so clear that it is not necessary to speak here of imitation. Coexistence of two waters, semantic opposition of happiness

at the birth of a new life (the life of a married couple as a whole) and the happiness of the end of earthly life, the transition to another world where water carries, appears quite transparently in the English proverb: Happy is the bride that the sun shines on, / Happy is the corpse that the rain rains on - lit. 'happy is that bride who marries on the day when the sun shines; happy is the dead on whom the rain falls' features from the past.

In England, it is a common tradition to wash the threshold boiling water when the bride leaves the house. The interpretation of the legend is as follows: this will speed up the marriage of the first unmarried girl whose dress gets wet on the threshold. As a rule, this applies to witnesses of the bride. New married in England wetting her shoes on the doorstep to secure a happy future. Undoubtedly, in this case, the threshold again acts as a mediator between the two worlds - the world of the living and the world of the dead and the change in social roles - the transition from the state unmarried to the state of married. Another bride in the groom's house hung towels, sprinkled with water housekeeping, throwing chicken into the oven, etc., etc. (combination of water and fire magic).

In the UK, the bride kept a piece of wedding cake for the first christening she attended; before the first sprinkling with holy water; to the first life-giving drops that fell on her during the rite of baptism. This consecrated piece became a guarantee that the bride could. Bael in Old English texts means both "funeral pyre" and "just fire". In a poem "Beowulf" we meet "bæl" in plots telling about the burning of the deceased hero at the stake: "he chose funeral fire" – He bael cure. The Old Norse word bal, cognate with it, also meant "funeral fire" [9, S. 66]. The presence in Old English of even two separate words for the designation of a funeral pyre reflects the relevance of this phenomenon in the culture and consciousness of the people.

Verbalization of water symbols in English being a mother. Sometimes English brides for this purpose keep the fudge, which was used to decorate the wedding cake on top, for the first christening. Thus, water, as one of the primary elements of the universe, is a long-standing universal symbol of all cultures of the world; it is associated with the primary matter and birth. That is why water is considered as the beginning and the end, the sacred beginning and at the same time the source of the birth of evil, death, which, accordingly, found its reflection in the language.

REFERENCE:

1. Агаркова Н. Э. Концепт «Деньги» как фрагмент английской языковой картины мира: автореф. дисс. ... к. филол. н. Иркутск, 2001. 20 с.
2. Гамкрелидзе Т. В., Иванов Вяч. Вс. Индоевропейский язык и индоевропейцы. Реконструкция и историкотипологический анализ праязыка и протокультуры. Тбилиси: Изд-во Тбилисского ун-та, 1984. 1331 с.
3. Которова Е. Г. Концепты «пространство» и «время» и некоторые особенности их репрезентации в кетском языке //
4. Bosworth J., Toller T. An Anglo-Saxon Dictionary. London: Oxford University Press; Amen House, 1954. 1302 p.